

READING SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES AS A TASK FOR STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the concept and main types of scientific articles, describes the main conditions and possibilities of using reading scientific articles in organizing independent work in the discipline "Finance", and gives one practical example of using a scientific article in the educational process.

The discipline "Finance" is one of the main disciplines studied by 2nd year undergraduate students, studying in various areas of study. The main goal of this discipline is to develop in future highly qualified economists knowledge of the theoretical and legal foundations of organizing financial relations in various fields, as well as skills and abilities for their practical use. Students must complete various types of tasks during independent study. The main types of independent work of students include taking notes of educational material (textbooks, teaching aids, lecture texts), writing essays, solving tests, writing abstracts, studying regulatory documents, analyzing practical and statistical data. Recently, more and more attention has been paid to teaching students the skills of conducting scientific work, preparing scientific articles and theses, as well as using original materials in Russian and foreign languages in the educational process. A scientific article is a logically completed study of a particular problem, carried out using the scientific method. There are different types of scientific articles [1-5]:

- scientific and theoretical articles that present theoretical developments in a certain field of science;
- scientific and practical articles that discuss the results of experimental research in a certain field of science and describe the results obtained;
- review articles that provide an overview of the opinions of various scientists (scientific schools) on a particular problem and the opinion of the author himself. The selection of a scientific article for students to take notes is made by the teacher, based on the requirements of the curriculum, the content of the academic discipline, the topic of the lecture and practical lesson. The sources of the article can be either a printed source of periodicals or Internet sites.

Let's consider the main conditions and possibilities of using reading scientific articles in organizing independent work in the discipline "Finance":

1. Students must have constant access to international databases of scientific publications, including Web of Science, Scopus, ScienceDirect, eLIBRARY.RU, Cyberleninka and others. Information resource centers of higher educational organizations have the necessary conditions for students to work with various databases of scientific publications, and qualified employees can teach them how to use them.
2. Students must have sufficient knowledge of foreign languages, for example, English. If students do not know English at a sufficient level, they must have the skills to use text translation programs, including Google Translator. It is also possible to complete the task of reading scientific articles in a foreign language in groups consisting of students with different levels of knowledge of the English language.
3. When using scientific articles in Russian and foreign languages as material for students' independent work, the teacher must focus on the students' level of knowledge of a given foreign language, as well as on the degree of complexity of the text.
4. The teacher can use scientific articles both in the process of preparing lecture material, adding the results of the latest research to his lecture texts, and as an assignment for students' independent work and an assignment for discussion during a practical lesson.
5. The teacher can select one or more scientific articles based on the topic of the current lesson in the discipline or one of the current problems of economic development. A scientific article may cover several topics in a discipline or may be important to study in terms of research methodology and the practice of writing a scientific article.

The teacher must determine what points students need to pay attention to when they work with a scientific article. Let's look at one practical example of using a scientific article in the educational process. One of the topics in the discipline "Finance" is "Financial Policy", within the framework of which the concept, essence, main instruments and directions of the state's financial policy are considered. One of the scientific articles that can be recommended to students for independent study on this topic is the article "Suggestions for a New Classification of Fiscal Tools", published by Elena Pădurean and Andreea Stoian in "Procedia Economics and Finance". The aim of this paper is to identify a set of fiscal tools through which fiscal policy can achieve its goals. Any adjustment policy, including fiscal policy, uses a number of tools in order to make an economic intervention. Some of these tools may have an administrative nature, others economic, etc. In this context, the method we use is to identify a list of the fundamental tools of fiscal policy, based on attributes that define the notion of fiscal instrument [6].

As a task for independent work, the teacher can tell the students to read this article, make a brief summary and answer the following questions:

- what is the title of this article?
- who is the author(s) of this article?
- in which scientific journal (collection of conference materials) this scientific article (thesis) was published;
- what information is provided in the abstract of this scientific article?
- what are the keywords?
- do these keywords correspond to the title of the article and the text of its abstract?

- what sections does this article consist of?
- what are the names of the sections of a scientific article?
- how is the list of used literature compiled?
- based on its study, can you say which sources were used by the authors of this article and why?
- based on studying the title of the article, abstract, keywords and list of references used, can you predict or predict what the main content of the article will be about? Write down the main ideas in your notebook;
- what information is provided in the first section of the article “The Financial Institution”?
- what is fiscal policy?
- what is the institutional basis for fiscal policy?
- which bodies have different powers in the field of fiscal policy?
- what is the legislative framework for the development and implementation of fiscal policy?
- what is described in the second section of the article “The Fiscal Tool”?
- what is a fiscal instrument?
- what are the characteristic features of a fiscal instrument?
- what is the purpose of using a fiscal instrument at the macroeconomic level?
- as information is provided in the third section of “The Classification of Fiscal Tools”?
- what are taxes?
- what are state budget expenditures?
- into what groups are fiscal instruments divided?
- what are fiscal instruments that generate revenue?
- what are fiscal instruments that affect taxpayers?
- what are fiscal rules?
- what fiscal rules do the authors describe?
- what new information did you gain from reading this article?
- what conclusions do the authors make at the end of the article?
- does the text of this article complement, confirm or refute your previously acquired knowledge?
- are there any controversial issues in this article that you would like to discuss during the practical lesson?
- how do the authors of this article justify their opinion?
- how can you use the information received in your further educational or scientific work?
- what new knowledge, skills, and abilities did you gain while performing this type of independent work?

Based on the results of reading this article, the teacher can give you the task of making notes. The structure of the abstract of a scientific article should include the following elements:

- bibliographic data: author, title, source of publication, date of publication, number of pages;
- information about the author: place of work, position, area of scientific (practical) activity;
- the main topic of the article, the goals of the article;
- plan (structure) of the article;

- the main provisions of the article in accordance with the plan;
- the conclusion made by the author of the article;
- source base of the article;
- the student's attitude towards the materials presented in the article.

Studying scientific articles in Russian and foreign languages is an interesting and informative type of independent work, useful both for students studying the content of the discipline "Finance", familiarizing themselves with the latest results of scientific research in the field of economics and finance of foreign scientists, and for acquiring skills and abilities to work with scientific literature.

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